

WAYS TO IMPROVE READING SKILLS

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Abstract: *Developing reading skills is incredibly important for early readers, starting as early as picture books. As school-aged children get older, it will make them understand textbooks, newspapers, and other more complex texts. Improving reading comprehension can help your students become successful readers in and out of the classroom for the rest of their lives.*

Key words: *reading skills, comprehension, reader, struggle, improve, develop, understand, vocabulary, knowledge, ability, lesson.*

What is reading and why is it one of the vital skills in academic performance? Reading comprehension is a reader’s ability to understand the explicit and implicit meaning of a text. It develops with vocabulary knowledge and word recognition to add meaning. When students use reading comprehension skills, they are turning words into thoughts and ideas.

Reading skills of the students is crucial to understand classroom coursework. But, it is not automatic. That is why the first and foremost goal of any English teacher is to build reading skills. Teachers love to share different stories and the subjects they are passionate about. However, helping children to develop the same interest requires foundational reading skills to comprehend and enjoy the lesson.

Many students find reading as one of the most difficult activities in English, especially if it is tied to lesson plans and learning complex information. They struggle with reading comprehension and understanding for a variety reasons:

- They prefer a different learning style
- They are not interested in reading and writing
- They don’t have the necessary prior knowledge to understand the text
- They have trouble focusing on one word at a time and skip important ideas
- They are working with a learning need like dyslexia that makes understanding written materials difficult

Reading is one of the most important ways for students and adults to learn new information. Reading comprehension can also help struggling readers build enjoyment of reading and participate more fully at lessons. And it is not just for the

classroom, either- reading comprehension has real-life applications for readers of all ages. It can:

- Equip readers to make good day-to-day decisions with available information
- Give readers the ability to think critically about what they read online and in the news
- Help readers decipher meaning in recipes, directions or other step-by-step instructions
- Help students move past word recognition into understanding and remembering the text

Vocabulary knowledge is the key of reading comprehension. Students with good vocabulary strategies understand what words mean and have the background knowledge to understand the given text. It also includes strategies for using context clues to determine the meaning of unfamiliar words. The reading comprehension process is over before it begins if students don't have solid vocabulary knowledge or the ability to learn new words.

Here are some simple and effective ways to help children to improve reading skills.

1. Annotate and highlight the text.
2. Personalize the content.
3. Practice problem solving skills.
4. Incorporate more senses.
5. Understand common themes
6. Set reading goals.
7. Read in portions.
8. Let students guide their reading.

In my opinion, every student deserves the chance to build critical comprehension skills. Whether you are teaching high school or elementary school students, it is never too late to use reading comprehension strategies to improve understanding, boost retention and make connections. Every student is different, so adjust your teaching methods accordingly!

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